

MONTE CARLO RADIATIVE TRANSFER MODEL FOR AIRLESS PLANETARY SURFACES

NITI SINGH

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
for the degree of Master of Science

MONTE CARLO RADIATIVE TRANSFER MODEL

For Airless Planetary Surfaces

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of the requirements for the degree of*

MASTER OF SCIENCE

By

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Dedicated to my Parents

*For their endless love, silent sacrifices, and the strength
they gave me even when I didn't ask for it.*

"I Solemnly Swear I am up to no good"

Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban

Declaration

I hereby declare that the thesis dissertation entitled “*Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer Model for Airless Planetary Surfaces*”, submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Master of Science in Physics** at the National Institute of Science Education and Research (NISER), Bhubaneswar, is an original work carried out solely by me under the supervision of **Dr. Guneshwar Thangjam** and **Dr. Tuhin Ghosh**, NISER Bhubaneswar. This research has been conducted in accordance with the academic and ethical guidelines prescribed by the Homi Bhabha National Institute (HBNI) for its research degree programmes. The contents of this dissertation have not been submitted for the award of any other degree or diploma. NISER is granted exclusive, royalty-free, and non-transferable rights to utilize this dissertation for research purposes, provided proper citation is maintained.

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The research presented in this thesis was conducted under my supervision at the School of Physical Sciences, National Institute of Science Education and Research (NISER), Bhubaneswar, India.

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Abstract

Complex radiative interactions within granular, inhomogeneous media govern the reflectance behaviour of airless planetary surfaces. In this work, we develop a Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) framework to simulate the bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) of particulate media aimed at applications in planetary science. In the 9th semester, a basic routine for both Direct and Indirect MCRT approaches are modelled which is improvised in the current semester to emulate semi-infinite regolith-like media by incorporating anisotropic scattering using the Henyey-Greenstein phase function, probabilistic photon tracking, and realistic boundary conditions.

The simulation environment is constructed with parametric flexibility in key physical characteristics such as single scattering albedo (SSA), volume filling factor (ϕ) and asymmetry parameter (b). Improvements in the model architecture resolve prior limitations in direction sampling and periodic boundary application, enabling the accurate reproduction of scattering behaviour, including the Shadow Hiding Opposition Effect (SHOE). The Indirect MCRT implementation, in particular, yields BRDF outputs with significantly reduced Monte Carlo noise and computational cost, thereby outperforming the direct method in both efficiency and precision.

Validation is performed against multiple theoretical formulations of Hapke's reflectance models (IMSA, H2008, AMSA) and existing literature-based MCRT simulations. The refined model demonstrates strong agreement, particularly in reproducing anisotropic multiple scattering and opposition surges. This indicates its suitability for extending to spectrally-resolved simulations and data-driven modelling of planetary bodies such as the Moon and Ceres. Future work can integrate wavelength-dependent optical constants and observational data to retrieve surface parameters such as grain size, porosity, and albedo with enhanced fidelity.

List of Symbols

ABBREVIATIONS

MCRT Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer

SYMBOLS

- α Photon propagation direction, represented as (θ, ψ) .
- α' Scattered photon direction.
- \mathbf{r} Position vector in 3D space.
- \mathbf{r}_i Intermediate scattering location of the i^{th} photon.
- ℓ Mean free path
- ϵ Emissivity of the planetary surface material
- $\kappa(\mathbf{r})$ Extinction coefficient at position \mathbf{r} .
- κ_{abs} Absorption coefficient.
- κ_{sca} Scattering coefficient
- λ Wavelength of the incident light.
- \mathcal{K} Porosity
- μ Cosine of the zenith angle, $\mu = \cos \theta$.
- ψ Azimuthal angle of the photon direction.
- ρ Number density of scatterers in the medium.
- ρ_{surf} Surface density
- σ_s Scattering cross-section
- τ Optical Depth of the slab medium.
- θ Zenith angle of the photon direction.

- b Asymmetry factor for the Henyey-Greenstein phase function.
- $d\Omega$ Differential solid angle element.
- $dI/d\tau$ Differential change in radiance with respect to optical depth.
- dI/ds Differential change in radiance with respect to path length.
- e Emission angle of scattered photons (in degrees).
- $e^{-\tau/\mu}$ Attenuation factor due to absorption and scattering along the path.
- E_0 Initial energy of the photon packet
- h_i or $V(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)$ Visibility function
- i Incidence angle of incoming photons (in degrees).
- $I(0, \mu)$ Incident radiance at the boundary surface.
- $I(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ Radiance at position \mathbf{r} in direction $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$.
- N Number of photon packets to simulate.
- $p(\boldsymbol{\alpha}', \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ Scattering phase function from direction $\boldsymbol{\alpha}'$ to $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$.
- $p(g_i)$ Single scattering phase function at the phase angle g_i
- s Path length travelled by a photon.
- $S(\tau, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ Source function at optical depth τ in direction $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$.
- rad or r Radius of particles in the medium

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Introduction

"When people say impossible, they usually mean improbable."

— *Nikolai Lantsov 'Sturmhond' : Siege and Storm*

Photons don't fight clouds or storms on airless worlds - they just hit the surface, scatter, and leave behind a BRDF-shaped signature. Without the chaos of weather systems or atmospheric interference, these barren landscapes become natural laboratories for exploring how light interacts with matter. Every reflected ray carries encoded information about the surface it touched: its roughness, grain size, composition, and even its history. This simplicity, however, is deceptive. Beneath the apparent straightforwardness of *"light in, light out"* lies a rich and complex interplay of physical processes that govern the reflectance behaviour of airless planetary bodies.

1.1 What are Airless Planetary Bodies?

Airless planetary bodies are celestial objects that lack an atmosphere. They possess a surface pressure significantly lower than $1 \mu\text{bar}$ (10^{-1} Pa), rendering it effectively devoid of a substantial atmosphere to significantly influence surface processes [1, 2]. These include small bodies like asteroids, moons, and dwarf planets, where there is no substantial gaseous envelope to influence surface conditions. The absence of an atmosphere means that radiative transfer (RT) is governed entirely by the surface and the regolith, i.e a layer of loose, fragmented material covering the solid bedrock, allowing for more straightforward modelling compared to planets with atmospheres.

No atmospheric interference and simplified modelling environment:

Airless planetary bodies offer a more controlled environment for studying radiative transfer. Since the radiation interacts directly with the surface and subsurface materials and there is no atmospheric medium to complicate the radiation transport, models can focus on the reflection, absorption, and scattering properties of the surface and regolith, without needing to account for complex interactions with an atmosphere [3].

Figure 1.1: Schematics of the processes on airless surfaces, i.e. Mercury and the Moon [4].

1.2 Radiative Transfer in Astrophysics and Planetary Science

Radiative transfer (RT) is a key concept in astrophysics and planetary science, referring to the process by which radiation is absorbed, scattered, and emitted by matter. Understanding how radiation interacts with the regolith of planetary bodies is crucial for interpreting observational data, especially for remote sensing applications, as it provides important clues about the physical and chemical properties of these bodies [5, 6].

The *Radiative Transfer Equation* (RTE) provides the fundamental framework for describing how radiation propagates through and interacts with a medium. In astrophysical and planetary contexts, it captures the balance between energy introduced into the radiation field and the energy removed or redistributed due to interactions with matter [7, 8].

$$\vec{\alpha} \cdot \nabla I(\vec{r}, \vec{\alpha}) = -\kappa_{\text{ext}}(\vec{r})I(\vec{r}, \vec{\alpha}) + \kappa_{\text{sca}}(\vec{r}) \int_{4\pi} P(\vec{\alpha}', \vec{\alpha})I(\vec{r}, \vec{\alpha}') d\Omega' + \epsilon(\vec{r}, \vec{\alpha}) \quad (1.1)$$

Here is a form of the RTE, describing the change in specific intensity $I(\vec{r}, \vec{\alpha})$ along direction $\vec{\alpha}$ due to extinction (absorption and scattering), in-scattering from other

directions weighted by the phase function $P(\vec{\alpha}', \vec{\alpha})$, and local emission $\epsilon(\vec{r}, \vec{\alpha})$, expressing the balance between radiative losses and gains in a medium [9–11].

Figure 1.2: Regolith distribution in airless surfaces [12].

However, solving analytically or deterministically in cases involving multiple scattering, irregular geometries, or heterogeneous media becomes challenging [13].

1.2.1 Electromagnetic Radiation in Remote Sensing

In planetary science, electromagnetic radiation - particularly light in the visible and infrared spectrum - is the primary means of probing planetary surfaces. Space-based telescopes, orbiters, and rovers rely on radiation reflected from planetary surfaces to gather data. This remote sensing enables scientists to infer surface composition, temperature, topography, and other characteristics, without having to physically visit or land on these bodies. The interpretation of this data depends on understanding how radiation interacts with the surface materials.

1.2.2 Reflectance Properties

The fraction of reflected photons from a planetary regolith with respect to the incident photons gives reflectance. It is a key quantity that helps planetary scientists derive the physical properties of the surface, such as its composition, roughness, and texture. Reflectance is affected by various factors, including the grain size and porosity of the regolith, surface roughness, and the presence of certain minerals.

- **Observed Reflectance:** The observed reflectance is a function of both the surface properties (e.g., material composition and texture) and the geometry of the incident and reflected radiation. It serves as a critical data point for understanding the planetary surface.

- **Surface and Subsurface Properties:** By analysing reflectance, scientists can infer the physical characteristics of planetary regoliths, such as particle size, mineral composition, and the presence of volatiles. The study of reflectance also helps in understanding processes like space weathering and impact gardening, which continuously alter the surface properties.

1.3 Reflectance Modelling

Reflectance modelling is the mathematical approach used to simulate how radiation interacts with planetary surfaces, with the goal of interpreting observed reflectance data. These models help in estimating the surface properties of planetary bodies, providing insights into their composition and physical characteristics. One important model used in reflectance studies is the **Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF)**.

BRDF: The BRDF is a vital quantity in reflectance modelling, as it defines how the reflectance of a surface varies with changes in the angle of incident light and the angle of observation. It provides a comprehensive description of the surface's optical properties.

Link Between Modelling and Physical Properties

Reflectance models are invaluable tools for extracting key physical properties of planetary surfaces, such as:

- **Surface Composition:** By comparing observed reflectance with model predictions, scientists can determine the mineralogical composition of the surface.
- **Particle Size:** Models can help estimate the size of the regolith particles by studying how the surface reflects light at different wavelengths.
- **Porosity and Roughness:** These properties influence how light is scattered and absorbed on the surface, and reflectance models can help quantify them.

Reflectance modelling also helps in understanding the evolution of planetary surfaces over time, providing insights into processes like space weathering, impact gardening, and regolith evolution.

1.3.1 Limitations in Traditional Models

Traditional models have been widely used to model reflectance. However, these models are based on simplifying assumptions that limit their accuracy [13] in some situations:

- **Simplifying Assumptions:** Analytic models like Hapke assume homogeneous surfaces and isotropic scattering, which may not fully capture the complexities of real planetary surfaces.
- **Surface Geometries and Subsurface Effects:** Traditional models struggle to handle complex surface geometries, like rough terrains, and multiple scattering interactions within the regolith.
- **Physical Accuracy:** While traditional models provide a good approximation, they may fail to accurately predict the reflectance in all conditions, especially when surface properties are heterogeneous or when there are complex interactions between radiation and the subsurface.

The Hapke model [14] is the most widely adopted analytical framework for modeling reflectance from particulate surfaces—especially those of airless bodies. It incorporates key physical parameters such as:

- w : single scattering albedo,
- $p(g)$: phase function dependent on scattering angle g ,
- $B_{SH}(g)$, $B_{CB}(g)$: opposition effects (Shadow Hiding and Coherent Backscattering),
- $S(\mu_{0e}, \mu_e, \psi)$: roughness and shadowing function,
- M : multiple scattering function.

The bidirectional reflectance function in Hapke’s formalism is given by:

$$r = K \frac{w}{4\pi} \frac{\mu_{0e}}{\mu_{0e} + \mu_e} \left[(1 + B_{SH}(g))p(g) + M \left(\frac{\mu_{0e}}{K}, \frac{\mu_e}{K}, g \right) \right] (1 + B_{CB}(g))S(\mu_{0e}, \mu_e, \psi) \quad (1.2)$$

In this equation, μ_{0e} and μ_e are the effective cosines of the incidence and emission angles, respectively, adjusted for roughness. The factor K includes the porosity correction. Brightness increases as the phase angle g approaches zero due to:

- **SHOE (Shadow Hiding Opposition Effect):** Caused by reduced shadowing at low phase angles.

- **CBOE (Coherent Backscatter Opposition Effect):** Due to constructive interference of light paths; often significant only at very small angles and sometimes neglected.

For instance, the Hapke model has proven powerful and has been widely validated using lunar and asteroid data [15, 16]; it makes several simplifying assumptions. These include isotropic or empirical phase functions, homogeneous media, and limited capacity to simulate complex geometries or heterogeneities.

1.4 Scope of the Thesis

This thesis focuses on the development and validation of a model for simulating the reflectance of airless planetary surfaces [17, 18]. The primary goal is to improve the accuracy of reflectance models by addressing limitations associated with traditional models, such as the Hapke model. The focus is on simulating radiation interactions with planetary surfaces more realistically [19–21].

The developed model will be validated against both experimental and observational data, comparing it with the results from traditional reflectance models and data from space missions such as those involving the Moon and Ceres. This comparison will help assess the accuracy and applicability of the model in various planetary environments.

Radiation Propagation in Airless Surfaces

"Before we get started, does anyone want to get out?"

— *Captain America: The Winter Soldier*

Understanding the scattering and absorption of light by particulate surfaces is fundamental to interpreting the spectral and photometric properties of airless surfaces. The radiative transfer equation (RTE) provides a mathematical framework to describe how radiation propagates through such a medium. For regolith-covered surfaces, where particles are densely packed and exhibit complex angular scattering behaviour, numerical methods such as Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) are indispensable for accurate modelling.

2.1 The Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE)

We start from the steady-state RTE in 3D for a non-emitting medium:

$$\hat{\alpha} \cdot \nabla I(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\alpha}) = -\kappa_{ext}(\mathbf{r})I(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\alpha}) + \kappa_{sca}(\mathbf{r}) \int_{4\pi} p(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\alpha}')I(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\alpha}') d\Omega' \quad (2.1)$$

The left-hand side represents the change in intensity I along direction $\hat{\alpha}$, and the right-hand side balances the extinction loss and scattering gain. The extinction coefficient κ_{ext} accounts for both absorption and scattering, while κ_{sca} is only for scattering [22, 23].

Define the single scattering albedo as $\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\kappa_{sca}(\mathbf{r})}{\kappa_{ext}(\mathbf{r})}$

$$\hat{\alpha} \cdot \nabla I(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\alpha}) = -\kappa_{ext}I(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\alpha}) + \kappa_{ext}\omega \int_{4\pi} p(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\alpha}')I(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\alpha}') d\Omega' \quad (2.2)$$

ω describes the fraction of interaction events that result in scattering. If $\omega = 1$, the medium is purely scattering; if $\omega = 0$, it's purely absorbing.

The Figure 2.1 shows the radiance I traveling through a solid angle $d\Omega$ toward a surface element dS from direction (θ, ψ) . This representation corresponds to the directional intensity term in the formal RTE solution and is key for defining the angular resolution of radiative transfer and flux calculation.

Figure 2.1: Radiance I propagating along a specified direction within a differential solid angle $d\Omega$, incident on a differential surface area dS [10]

Convert spatial variable z to optical depth τ :

$$\tau(z) = \int_z^\infty \kappa_{ext}(z') dz' \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{d}{dz} = -\kappa_{ext} \frac{d}{d\tau} \quad (2.3)$$

Optical depth τ represents how opaque a medium is from the top ($\tau = 0$) down to a depth z . The negative sign arises because depth increases downward.

In 1D plane-parallel geometry, directional dependence reduces to cosine of zenith angle, $\mu = \cos \theta$:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\alpha} \cdot \nabla &\rightarrow \mu \frac{d}{d\tau} \\ \Rightarrow \mu \frac{dI(\tau, \mu)}{d\tau} &= -I(\tau, \mu) + \omega \int_{4\pi} p(\mu, \mu') I(\tau, \mu') d\Omega' \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

The 3D directional derivative collapses into a single angular variable μ due to symmetry, giving a scalar RTE that depends only on depth and zenith direction. Now we use azimuthal symmetry to reduce the phase function and solid angle integral:

$$d\Omega' = d\psi' d\mu' \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{4\pi} \rightarrow \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-1}^1$$

If the phase function depends only on μ, μ' , i.e., $p(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\alpha}') = p(\mu, \mu')$, then:

$$\int_{4\pi} p(\mu, \mu') I(\tau, \mu') d\Omega' = \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi' \int_{-1}^1 p \cdot I \cdot d\mu' = 2\pi \int_{-1}^1 p(\mu, \mu') I(\tau, \mu') d\mu' \quad (2.5)$$

Define normalized phase function: $\frac{1}{2}p(\mu, \mu')$, so:

$$\int_{4\pi} \rightarrow 2\pi \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \rightarrow \int_{-1}^1$$

Scalar integro-differential RTE in 1D plane-parallel geometry:

$$\mu \frac{dI(\tau, \mu)}{d\tau} = I(\tau, \mu) - \frac{\omega}{2} \int_{-1}^1 p(\mu, \mu') I(\tau, \mu') d\mu' \quad (2.6)$$

The left-hand side represents the attenuation of intensity along direction μ . The right-hand side consists of two parts: $I(\tau, \mu)$: local loss due to extinction, Integral term: gain due to scattering of photons from other directions μ' into μ , modulated by the phase function and ω .

2.2 Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) Model

Monte Carlo radiative transfer (MCRT) is a powerful numerical technique used to model the propagation of radiation through a medium. This method is particularly valuable in scenarios where the medium is complex, such as in astrophysics, planetary science, and medical physics [6, 24, 25].

Unlike traditional deterministic approaches, which attempt to solve the RTE by discretising space and time, MCRT directly simulates the physical processes of radiation transport through statistical simulation of photon paths, treating radiation as a collection of discrete particles or rays [26–28]. It is based on the probabilistic nature of radiation interactions with matter, where each photon or energy quantum is treated as a particle that follows a random path determined by the physics of scattering, absorption, and emission [9, 23, 29]. Each photon or ray is followed as it interacts with the medium.

Figure 2.2: Graphical depiction of Monte Carlo simulation procedure [30].

At its core, MCRT simulates the behaviour of large numbers of photon packets, each representing a portion of the total radiation. By using random sampling methods, the MCRT technique tracks the trajectory of each packet and computes how it is affected by the medium [31]. MCRT can be used to model complex, heterogeneous, anisotropic media and geometries [32, 33]. This makes it particularly useful for problems that involve scattering in irregular or multi-dimensional spaces, where traditional models often struggle and exact solutions are difficult or impossible to obtain analytically.

2.3 From RTE to MC-RTE

To implement a Monte Carlo solution, we first rewrite the RTE in integral form. Consider a photon path of direction μ starting at optical depth τ and moving toward the observer. The formal solution for the specific intensity in this direction can be written as (2.6). To interpret this stochastically, consider that a photon is emitted from the source and travels a distance determined by an optical depth τ sampled from an exponential distribution [22, 23]. At each point, there is a probability ω that it scatters and $1 - \omega$ that it is

absorbed. If it scatters, the new direction is sampled from the phase function $p(\mu, \mu')$.

The Figure 2.3 illustrates the geometry of radiative transfer between two points P_1 and P_2 within a scattering medium. The directions of incident and scattered rays (i_1, i_2) are defined using spherical angles (θ_1, ψ_1) and (θ_2, ψ_2) respectively. These angles define the direction vectors $\alpha_1 \equiv (\theta_1, \psi_1)$, $\alpha_2 \equiv (\theta_2, \psi_2)$, which are essential for evaluating the phase function $p(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$ in the scattering source term of the RTE.

Figure 2.3: Scattering geometry in spherical coordinates, showing initial and scattered directions α_1 and α_2 between two points within a participating medium.

The Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE) in plane-parallel geometry describes how the specific intensity $I(\tau, \mu)$ changes along an optical path through a medium. The direction of radiation is described using $\mu = \cos \theta$, and τ is the optical depth along the path. The integro-differential form of the RTE [34] is given by:

$$\mu \frac{dI(\tau, \mu)}{d\tau} = -I(\tau, \mu) + (1 - \omega)B(\tau) + \omega \int_{-1}^1 p(\mu', \mu) I(\tau, \mu') d\mu' \quad (2.7)$$

Here, ω is the single scattering albedo, which quantifies the proportion of extinction (combined absorption and scattering) due to scattering alone. The Planck function $B(\tau)$ represents thermal emission at optical depth τ . The integral term thus captures the

contribution of in-scattered light from all other directions.

To solve this equation analytically or numerically, especially in Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT), it is advantageous to recast it into an integral form. We first isolate the source term $S(\tau, \mu)$ as the sum of thermal and in-scattered contributions:

$$S(\tau, \mu) = (1 - \omega)B(\tau) + \omega \int_{-1}^1 p(\mu', \mu) I(\tau, \mu') d\mu'$$

This turns the RTE into a first-order linear ODE:

$$\mu \frac{dI(\tau, \mu)}{d\tau} + I(\tau, \mu) = S(\tau, \mu)$$

Multiplying by the integrating factor $e^{\tau/\mu}$, we obtain:

$$\frac{d}{d\tau} \left(e^{\tau/\mu} I(\tau, \mu) \right) = \frac{1}{\mu} e^{\tau/\mu} S(\tau, \mu)$$

Integrating this from the surface (0) to optical depth τ , we get the formal integral solution:

$$I(\tau, \mu) = I(0, \mu) e^{-\tau/\mu} + \frac{1}{\mu} \int_0^\tau S(t, \mu) e^{-(\tau-t)/\mu} dt$$

Physically, the first term represents the attenuated incoming intensity from the surface boundary, while the second term accumulates the source contributions from all points t along the path, each attenuated by the exponential factor $e^{-(\tau-t)/\mu}$, which reflects extinction between source and observer.

Substituting the source term back into the integral, the final expression becomes:

$$I(\tau, \mu) = I(0, \mu) e^{-\tau/\mu} + \frac{1}{\mu} \int_0^\tau \left[(1 - \omega)B(t) + \omega \int_{-1}^1 p(\mu', \mu) I(t, \mu') d\mu' \right] e^{-(\tau-t)/\mu} dt$$

This equation is the foundation for Monte Carlo simulation. Each term corresponds to a photon history: the free path (governed by the exponential term), the interaction type (determined by ω), and the direction of scattering (sampled from $p(\mu', \mu)$). By tracing many such photon paths and averaging their contributions, the MCRT method builds up the solution to the RTE statistically.

2.3.1 Direct and Indirect MCRT

Direct Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (Direct MCRT) focuses on the explicit simulation of photon transport from a radiation source through a medium to a detector. In Direct

MCRT, radiation emits from a defined source, the trajectories are then traced as it travels through the medium, undergoing interactions such as scattering and absorption. This method is particularly effective in scenarios where the direct paths of photons and their primary interactions are of interest, such as in imaging or in the study of radiation beams [9, 35].

The contribution to the emergent intensity in direction μ is computed by tallying only the photons that escape in that direction. Let a photon undergo n scattering events before exiting the surface. The contribution of a single photon path γ can be expressed as:

$$W_n(\gamma) = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n \omega p(\mu_{i+1}, \mu_i) e^{-\tau_i/|\mu_i|} \right) e^{-\tau_{n+1}/|\mu_{n+1}|} \quad (2.8)$$

Here, μ_i is the direction cosine of the i -th segment, τ_i is the optical depth between interactions, and ω is the scattering albedo. The exponential terms account for attenuation along each path segment.

Averaging over many such photon histories gives the Monte Carlo estimate of emergent intensity:

$$I_{emergent}(\mu) \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{esc}} W(\gamma_j) \quad (2.9)$$

This formulation only includes paths that exit the medium in direction μ , making it efficient for computing angular-dependent reflectance [36].

Indirect Monte Carlo radiative transfer (Indirect MCRT) emphasises the treatment of scattered radiation and diffuse light transport within the medium. Instead of focusing solely on the direct paths of photons from the source, Indirect MCRT accounts for the multiple scattering events that photons undergo, significantly contributing to the overall radiation field [37]. This approach is crucial in environments where scattering dominates, such as in planetary atmospheres or within dense interstellar clouds.

Figure 2.4: Path traced by photons in MCRT

To compute the probability that a photon observed in direction μ could have originated from the illumination source, undergoing a sequence of scatterings. For each backward photon path of n interactions, the weight is calculated as:

$$W_n(\gamma) = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n \omega p(\mu_i, \mu_{i-1}) e^{-\tau_i/|\mu_i|} \right) e^{-\tau_0/|\mu_0|} \cdot f(\mu_0) \quad (2.10)$$

Here, $f(\mu_0)$ represents the incoming illumination from the source in direction μ_0 , and the last exponential factor gives attenuation from the last scattering point to the surface. Summing over all such backward paths and averaging yields:

$$I(\mu) \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N W(\gamma_j) \quad (2.11)$$

Indirect MCRT is advantageous when dealing with small detector solid angles or narrow angular bins, as all simulated photons contribute directly to the estimated quantity.

Modelling the Photon Propagation

“I haven’t a clue what’s going on here but I’ll act like I do.”

— *Naruto Uzumaki : Naruto Shonen*

Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) provides a stochastic solution to the RTE by simulating the path histories of a large number of photons as they interact with the medium.

3.1 Physical Parameters in MCRT

This section presents and explains the physical parameters critical to the MCRT modelling of planetary surface reflectance. These parameters are grouped based on their physical relevance and role in the simulation, with emphasis on their physical meaning, mathematical formulation, and impact on the simulation results.

3.1.1 Scattering Behaviour in Particulate Media

These parameters define the optical and physical characteristics of regolith particles, which govern how photons interact with the surface. They influence scattering, absorption, and the overall angular distribution of reflected light.

Single Scattering Albedo (ω): The single scattering albedo quantifies the probability of a photon being scattered instead of being absorbed when the light interacts with the regolith [38]. It is defined as:

$$\omega = \frac{\kappa_{\text{sca}}}{\kappa_{\text{sca}} + \kappa_{\text{abs}}}$$

where κ_{sca} and κ_{abs} are the scattering and absorption coefficients, respectively. A higher ω implies more reflective (scattering-dominated) surfaces, while lower values indicate more absorbing materials.

Absorption and Scattering Coefficients: The extinction of light in a medium is characterised by two key parameters: the absorption coefficient κ_{abs} and the scattering coefficient κ_{sca} . These are related to the total extinction coefficient κ_{ext} by:

$$\kappa_{\text{ext}} = \kappa_{\text{abs}} + \kappa_{\text{sca}}$$

The absorption coefficient quantifies the rate at which photons are absorbed per unit path length, converting radiative energy into heat or other internal forms. The scattering coefficient describes the rate of redirection of photons without energy loss.

Single Scattering Phase Function $P(g)$: It gives the angular distribution of photons scattered by a single particle relative to the incident direction. It determines the probability of light scattering in a certain direction and is crucial for simulating the Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF). One of the most widely used analytic forms is the HG phase function, defined as:

$$P(g) = \frac{1 - b^2}{(1 + b^2 - 2b \cos g)^{3/2}} \quad (3.1)$$

Here, g is the phase angle, and b is the asymmetry parameter. The HG function captures anisotropic scattering, where scattering is not uniform in all directions. The simplicity and tunability of the HG function make it a practical choice for modelling planetary regolith surfaces. However, for surfaces with complex microstructures, empirical phase functions or multi-parameter generalisations of HG may be necessary.

Asymmetry Parameter (b): The asymmetry parameter b is a measure of the effect of anisotropy in an event of scattering. The value of b quantifies how much scattering is biased towards certain directions, particularly forward scattering, which is a common characteristic of planetary surface interactions. Depending on the value of b :

- $b = 0$ represents **isotropic scattering**, where light is scattered equally in all directions.
- $b > 0$ corresponds to **forward scattering**, where photons are more likely to be scattered in the direction of the incoming light.
- $b < 0$ indicates **backward scattering**, where photons are preferentially scattered away from the incident direction.

In the context of planetary surfaces, **forward scattering** (with $b > 0$) is commonly observed due to the properties of granular surfaces, regolith, or dust. The parameter b plays a crucial role in determining the **reflectance** and **phase function** of the surface, which are essential for modelling the interaction of light with planetary materials. In a Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) simulation, b directly influences the **scattering events** and **photon transport**, affecting how light is diffused across the surface.

Porosity \mathcal{K} : Porosity influences anisotropy both by altering the filling factor ϕ and the mean free path ℓ . In denser media (lower porosity), photons undergo more interactions, increasing the contribution of multiple scattering and leading to diffused anisotropy. The filling factor ϕ is directly related to porosity \mathcal{K} as:

$$\mathcal{K} = 1 - \phi$$

This relation shows how structural properties of the surface affect radiative transport, beyond just microscopic scattering.

Filling Factor (ϕ): The filling factor is the volume fraction of solid particles within a unit volume. It relates to porosity and affects the photon mean free path. Higher filling factors lead to more frequent interactions and stronger multiple scattering.

Opposition Effect: The opposition effect is a pronounced surge in brightness observed at very low phase angles ($g \rightarrow 0$). It is particularly evident for airless planetary bodies and is attributed to two major physical mechanisms:

1. **Shadow Hiding Opposition Effect (SHOE):** At small phase angles, shadows cast by surface particles are hidden from the observer, increasing the apparent brightness.
2. **Coherent Backscatter Opposition Effect (CBOE):** Constructive interference of photons travelling along reciprocal paths enhances reflectance in the backwards direction.

Particle Radius (rad): The radius of regolith particles affects the scattering regime through the size parameter $x = \frac{2\pi \cdot rad}{\ell}$. Small particles (Rayleigh regime) scatter light differently than larger particles (Mie or geometric optics regimes). While not always directly simulated, rad influences derived parameters like ω and $P(g)$.

Figure 3.1: Illustration of some of the key parameters based on Hapke Model [39].

Scattering Conditions:

- **Rayleigh Regime** ($x \ll 1$): For very small particles (compared to the wavelength), light is scattered in a way that depends on the wavelength as λ^{-4} and the size of the particles. This regime typically leads to scattering that is more uniform and isotropic.
- **Mie Regime** ($x \approx 1$): For particles of size comparable to the wavelength of light, the scattering is more complex, with significant angular dependence and more pronounced forward scattering and larger scattering cross-sections.
- **Geometric Optics Regime** ($x \gg 1$): For large particles, light behaves more like rays, and phenomena like reflection, refraction, and diffraction become more prominent.

3.1.2 Illumination and Observation Geometry

These geometric parameters define how the planetary surface is illuminated and observed. They are crucial for calculating bidirectional reflectance and phase curves.

Incidence Angle (i): It is the angle between the incoming photon beam and the surface normal. It influences how much energy is deposited and how deeply photons penetrate the surface. Grazing incidence increases shadowing and surface roughness.

Emission Angle (e): It is the angle between the surface normal and the observer’s direction. It determines how photons exit the surface and contributes to the angular dependence of the BRDF.

Phase Angle (g): It is the total angle between the illumination and observation directions, defined as $g = i + e$. It governs the shape of the reflectance phase curve and highlights effects such as opposition surge at low phase angles.

Azimuthal Angle (ψ): This is the angle between the incident and emergent rays in the plane tangent to the surface [40]. It is important in full BRDF modelling and for anisotropic or rough surfaces, although sometimes neglected in 1D simulations. Thus geometrically:

$$P(g, \psi) = p(g) \cdot p'(\psi)$$

3.1.3 Simulation Parameters

These parameters control the computational implementation of photon transport in the MCRT model.

Number of Photons (N): The total number of photon packets simulated determines the statistical accuracy of the model. Larger N reduces noise and improves the smoothness of phase curves, but increases computation time.

Optical Depth (τ): Optical depth quantifies the cumulative attenuation of light along a path:

$$\tau = \int \kappa_{\text{ext}}(s) ds$$

where κ_{ext} is the extinction coefficient. It governs how deeply photons penetrate into the surface before being absorbed or scattered.

Mean Free Path (ℓ): The mean distance light can travel between successive scattering events in a medium [26]. It is expressed as:

$$\ell = \frac{1}{\sigma_s \rho}$$

A smaller mean free path suggests more frequent scattering, influencing the photon transport and reflectance properties of the surface.

Step Size (Δs): The distance a photon travels before interacting is sampled from an exponential distribution:

$$\Delta s = -\ell \ln(R)$$

where $R \in (0, 1]$ is a random number and ℓ is the mean free path.

Scattering Events per Photon: This represents the number of interactions a photon undergoes before escaping or being absorbed. It is a measure of the multiple scattering regime and is statistically analysed in the model.

Statistical Convergence and Normalisation: The reflectance estimated via Monte Carlo simulation approaches the true value as the number of photon packets N increases. The statistical estimate for reflectance at a particular geometry (i, e, g) is:

$$R(i, e, g) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{esc}}} w_j \quad (3.2)$$

The statistical uncertainty decreases as $1/\sqrt{N}$, following the central limit theorem.

3.2 Modelling the MCRT Routine

The MCRT routines involve generating photon packets that simulate radiation incident on a particulate planetary surface. Each packet is tracked through stochastic interactions like scattering, absorption, and re-emission, governed by the optical properties of the surface [20, 41]. The model accounts for parameters such as SSA, phase function, and filling factor to simulate realistic surface reflectance [8, 42, 43].

To determine the interaction probabilities (scattering, absorption, and transmission) and the slab depth for a system of spherical particles with a **mono-disperse distribution** and filling factor (ϕ), we proceed step-by-step. This involves making initial assumptions and using appropriate mathematical relations.

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_s + \sigma_a$$

Given the SSA w , the relationship between σ_s and σ_t is:

$$\sigma_s = w \cdot \sigma_t \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_a = (1 - w) \cdot \sigma_t$$

The optical depth (τ) for the slab is related to the filling factor (ϕ), extinction cross-section (σ_t), and slab depth (d) as follows:

$$\tau = \frac{\phi\sigma_t d}{V_{\text{particle}}}$$

Where $V_{\text{particle}} = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_0^3$ is the volume of a single particle.

Substituting V_{particle} , we get:

$$\tau = \frac{\phi\sigma_t d}{\frac{4}{3}\pi r_0^3}$$

To meet the transmission requirement $P_{\text{trans}} < 1\%$, we need the optical depth to be greater than $\ln(100) \approx 4.605$, i.e.,

$$\tau > 4.605$$

Thus, the slab depth d is determined by rearranging the optical depth equation:

$$d > \frac{4.605 \cdot \frac{4}{3}\pi r_0^3}{\phi\sigma_t}$$

Figure 3.2: Simulated photon propagation in the medium with $N = 2 \times 10^4$ at $i = 0^\circ$.

For **geometric optics** with spherical particles, the extinction cross-section is related to the particle radius (r_0) and the extinction efficiency factor (Q_t):

$$\sigma_t = \pi r_0^2 Q_t$$

The extinction efficiency Q_t depends on the particle size relative to the wavelength of light. For large particles ($r_0 \gg \lambda$), Q_t is typically around 2. The scattering cross-section is given by:

$$\sigma_s = w \cdot \sigma_t = w \cdot \pi r_0^2 Q_t$$

Using $w = 0.5$, the scattering cross-section becomes:

$$\sigma_s = 0.5 \cdot \pi r_0^2 Q_t$$

Substitute the expression for σ_t into the equation for d :

$$d > \frac{4.605 \cdot \frac{4}{3} \pi r_0^3}{\phi \pi r_0^2 Q_t}$$

Simplifying:

$$d > \frac{4.605 \cdot \frac{4}{3} r_0}{\phi Q_t}$$

For $r_0 = 1 \mu m$ and $Q_t \approx 2$, this gives:

$$d > \frac{4.605 \cdot \frac{4}{3} \cdot 1 \mu m}{0.2 \cdot 2} \approx 7.68 \mu m$$

Thus, the slab depth d must be at least $8 \mu m$ to ensure that transmission is below 1%.
 Determining Interaction Probabilities: Now that we have determined the slab depth and other parameters, we can calculate the interaction probabilities:

$$P_{\text{scat}} = \frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_t} = w$$

For $w = 0.5$, this means 50% of interactions result in scattering.

$$P_{\text{abs}} = 1 - P_{\text{scat}} = 1 - w = 0.5$$

This means 50% of the interactions result in absorption. The transmission probability P_{trans} is given by:

$$P_{\text{trans}} = e^{-\tau}$$

With the calculated optical depth τ , we can determine how much light is transmitted through the slab. Since $\tau > 4.605$, P_{trans} will be less than 1%, satisfying the transmission requirement. A schematic geometry [6] of a scattering event is shown in Fig. 2.3 where the photon is originally propagating into direction $P_1(\theta', \phi')$ will scatter through Θ into direction $P_2(\theta, \phi)$ [44, 45].

In the direct method, the photon packet is traced step-by-step until it reaches the observer or is absorbed, with each scattering event and energy loss accounted for. The visibility of the photon packet is checked to see if it can be traced back to the light source without obstruction, contributing to the total energy reaching the observer.

Figure 3.3: Particulate medium in airless surfaces [12].

In the indirect method, the photon packet's energy is accumulated based on the phase angle and scattering probability, accounting for multiple scattering events until the photon either escapes or is absorbed. The cumulative energy and angular distribution of the scattered photons are then used to compute the reflectance.

After n scatterings:

$$E_m = \sum_{i=1}^n E_0 w^i \frac{p(g_i)}{4\pi} h_i \quad (3.3)$$

where h_i is 0 or 1, indicating whether the photon packet is visible from the source (1 if visible, 0 if not) [17]. The total energy for N photon packets is:

$$E = \sum_{m=1}^N E_m \quad (3.4)$$

This method requires repeating the process for a large number of photon packets to ensure statistical accuracy. The final reflectance is determined by averaging the energy of the photon packets reaching the observer, with the reflectance proportional to the ratio of scattered photons in each direction.

3.3 Model Implementation and Simulation Design

Figure 3.4: Flowchart for MCRT Simulation Algorithm

The simulation setup involves the development of a Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) model based on the routine described. The simulation is implemented using stochastic sampling to model photon trajectories and surface interactions. This framework allows for flexible adjustments of surface properties and illumination conditions.

The medium in this simulation in which scattering occurs has been described as a semi-infinite, approximated to a horizontal slab of spherical particles [17]. The depth of the slab is chosen to ensure that light transmission through the medium is sufficiently low, typically less than 1%. This condition ensures that the medium effectively absorbs and scatters most of the incoming light, mimicking the behaviour of a semi-infinite medium. In addition, the medium is defined by a filling factor, representing the volume fraction of the slab occupied by the particles. This factor is crucial in determining the optical density and interaction properties of the medium.

Figure 3.5: Volumes of simulated particulate media with different filling factor.

The particles within the medium are assumed to be of uniform size and spherical in shape. This uniformity simplifies the calculations and allows for the use of well-established scattering theories to describe the interaction of light with the particles. The SSA represents the probability of photon scattering. Furthermore, the single scattering phase function, typically derived from the Henyey-Greenstein Function [46] for spherical particles, describes the angular distribution of scattered light.

3.3.1 Model Geometry and Boundary Conditions

The medium is modelled as a finite box with horizontal dimensions defined by the number of particles and the filling factor. Periodic boundary conditions allow photons exiting one lateral wall to re-enter on the opposite side with the same propagation direction and depth. This effectively mimics an infinite horizontal extension, ensuring photons interact consistently without artificial boundary losses. These conditions maintain the statistical integrity of photon interactions, ensuring the simulation accurately represents a semi-infinite medium while preserving total energy within the system.

3.3.2 Defined Factors and Parameters

- N = Number of photon packets to be simulated (2×10^4 in this case to reduce the computational time).
- rad = Radius of the particles in the medium ($1 \mu\text{m}$).
- w = Single scattering albedo values to simulate ($[0.7, 0.5, 0.2]$).
- Isotropic and anisotropic scattering considered.

- i = Incidence angle of the incoming light (30°).
- b = Asymmetry factor.
- ϕ = Volume fraction occupied by particles.
- `slab_depth` = Depth of the slab medium ($10 \mu\text{m}$).
- Semi-infinite medium with periodic boundary conditions.
- Henyey-Greenstein phase function used as a single particle phase function.

The **HG phase function** [46] provides a simple analytical expression that can be easily implemented in simulations by Eq. 3.1 :

$$p(g) = \frac{1 - b^2}{4\pi(1 + b^2 + 2b \cos(g))^{3/2}}$$

3.4 Validating MCRT

We primarily validate its outputs against the results presented by **Ciarniello et al. (2014)** [17] to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the developed MCRT model. Their study employed an MC ray-tracing approach to simulate the bidirectional reflectance of particulate surfaces, particularly focusing on planetary regolith analogues. Their simulations accounted for multiple scattering events, surface roughness, and varying optical properties, producing reflectance data across a range of incidence, emission, and phase angles.

3.4.1 Overview of Hapke's Models

Hapke's bidirectional reflectance (BDR) theory has undergone several refinements over the years, evolving from the initial IMSA model to the AMSA model, and finally to the H2008 and H2012 models. This section summarises the key aspects of these models, emphasising their differences and limitations. It is worth noting that the correction for the Coherent Backscattering Opposition Effect (CBOE), introduced by Hapke (2002) [47], is excluded here since it is not applicable in the geometrical optics limit and is only significant for phase angles $g < 1^\circ\text{--}2^\circ$.

Figure 3.6: Reflectances simulations by [17] - indirect (black) and direct (grey).

3.4.1.1 IMSA Model

The Isotropic Multiple Scattering Approximation (IMSA), as proposed by Hapke (1993) [14], expresses the bidirectional reflectance as:

$$r(i, e, g) = \frac{w}{4\pi} \frac{\mu_0}{\mu_0 + \mu} [(1 + B_{SH}(g))p(g) + H(\mu)H(\mu_0) - 1] \quad (3.5)$$

Here $B_{SH}(g)$ represents the Shadow Hiding Opposition Effect (SHOE) given by:

$$B_{SH}(g) = \frac{B_0}{1 + (1/h) \tan(g/2)} \quad (3.6)$$

where B_0 is amplitude; h is the angular HWHM. For monodisperse particle distributions, h can be related to the medium filling factor ϕ as:

$$h = \frac{3}{8 \ln(1/\phi)} \quad (3.7)$$

Multiple scattering is modelled using Chandrasekhar's H -function [11], approximated under the assumption of isotropic scattering as:

$$H(x, w) = \frac{1 + 2x}{1 + 2cx}, \quad \text{where } c = \sqrt{1 - w} \quad (3.8)$$

3.4.1.2 AMSA Model

The Anisotropic Multiple Scattering Approximation (AMSA), introduced by Hapke (2002) [48], improves upon the IMSA model by providing a more accurate, though still approximate, representation of multiple scattering without assuming isotropy. The BDR in this model is expressed as:

$$r(i, e, g) = \frac{w}{4\pi} \frac{\mu_0}{\mu_0 + \mu} [(1 + B_{SH}(g))p(g) + M(w, \mu_0, \mu)] \quad (3.9)$$

The multiple scattering term M is defined as:

$$M(\mu_0, \mu) = P(\mu_0)[H(\mu) - 1] + P(\mu)[H(\mu_0) - 1] + P[H(\mu) - 1][H(\mu_0) - 1] \quad (3.10)$$

where $P(\mu)$ and P are angular averages involving the phase function $p(g)$ (detailed in Hapke, 2002 [48]).

3.4.1.3 H2008 and H2012 Models

Hapke (2008) introduced a further refinement by incorporating the effect of porosity, motivated by studies showing that densely packed particulate media appear brighter than more porous ones. Unlike previous models that treat absorption in a continuous medium, the H2008 model assumes a layered structure of discrete particles. The BDR expression in H2008 is:

$$r(i, e, g) = K \frac{w}{4\pi} \frac{\mu_0}{\mu_0 + \mu} [p(g) + H(\mu_0)H(\mu) - 1] \quad (3.11)$$

The factor K accounts for the porosity and depends on the filling factor ϕ :

$$K = \frac{\ln(1 - 1.209 \phi^{2/3})}{-1.209 \phi^{2/3}} \quad (3.12)$$

In this model, the Chandrasekhar H -function is modified accordingly:

$$H(x) = \frac{1 + 2x/K}{1 + 2cx/K} \quad (3.13)$$

Hapke (2012) [14] later extended this model to include SHOE, similar to its treatment in the IMSA model, but with an updated expression for h :

$$h = \frac{3K\phi}{8} \quad (3.14)$$

The complete BDR formulation with the opposition effect included becomes:

$$r(i, e, g) = K \frac{w}{4\pi} \frac{\mu_0}{\mu_0 + \mu} [(1 + B_{SH}(g))p(g) + H(\mu_0)H(\mu) - 1] \quad (3.15)$$

This final version is referred to as the H2012 model. Notably, as $\phi \rightarrow 0$, $K \rightarrow 1$, and the H2008 and H2012 models converge to the IMSA model, representing the limit of highly porous (sparse) media.

Results

“That’s not going to haunt us for the rest of our lives at all.”

— *Anxiety, Inside out 2*

The MCRT models using both direct and indirect methods were modelled according to the parameters and conditions as discussed in Section 3.3. However, several issues were encountered in the simulation results from last semester.

4.1 Previous Work

In the previous semester, the model could only incorporate the effects of a few parameters, like ϕ on the simulated particulate medium, which was illustrated in Fig. 3.5.

Figure 4.1: Direct MCRT Simulation

Notably, the plots in fig. 4.1 and fig. 4.2 did not show any effect of the incidence angle or any peaks corresponding to the Shadow Hiding Opposition Effect (SHOE) [14]. This

absence of expected features suggested that certain aspects of the model or its implementation needed further refinements.

Varying the asymmetry parameter had minimal impact on results, suggesting issues in how anisotropy was incorporated. Discrepancies were found between reflectance outputs from direct and indirect MCRT methods due to improper normalisation. This was expected to resolve once boundary conditions and anisotropy issues are addressed.

Figure 4.2: Indirect MCRT Simulation

The expected effects of single scattering albedo (w) on reflectance curves were successfully reproduced, indicating correct implementation of these aspects. To support debugging, photon paths were spatially simulated to allow the visualisation of propagation in 2D without excessive runtimes, as shown in Appendix A. The major challenges in these results were:

- The opposition effect (OE), specifically the shadow hiding opposition effect (SHOE), was not apparent.
- Anisotropic scattering was inaccurately represented due to improper direction updates.
- The normalisation of the reflectance values was incorrect.

4.2 Progress: Model Refinement and corrections

In the current semester, significant advancements have been made to both the Direct and Indirect Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) models. Building upon the preliminary versions developed earlier, the focus shifted toward incorporating missing physical effects, enhancing model accuracy, and expanding the framework to better capture surface scattering behavior on airless planetary bodies.

Figure 4.3: Current Direct MCRT model’s results against last semester’s result - Evident normalisation mismatch.

The new refined version addressed these issues significantly. One of the major corrections was related to periodic boundary conditions (PBCs). Initially, the PBCs were erroneously applied in the z -direction (depth), which caused photons to be confined within the top layer of the medium, bouncing repeatedly within a single particle without penetrating the medium. Physically, this prevented realistic photon propagation in depth. The corrected implementation applies PBCs only in the x and y directions, effectively simulating an infinite horizontal distribution of particles, while the z -axis captures depth penetration properly.

The previous method of sampling scattering directions ignored the initial photon propagation vector, applying fixed-frame angle changes instead. This resulted in the loss of sensitivity to the incidence angle and anisotropy. The improved model updates the new direction about the photon's current direction, preserving the anisotropic nature of scattering described by the Henyey-Greenstein phase function [46].

(a) $i=30^\circ$, $b=0$, $\phi=0.2$

(b) $i=60^\circ$, $b=0.2$, $\phi=0.1$

(c) $i=60^\circ$, $b=-0.2$, $\phi=0.1$

Figure 4.4: Current Indirect MCRT model's results against last semester's result.

Further, to incorporate the opposition effect accurately, the scattering events are now simulated using the **intersection point method** of photons with particles rather than

at *particle centre* scattering. This physically models the phenomenon of shadow hiding - photons travelling close to the line of sight are more likely to be scattered back because they are not hidden behind other particles.

4.2.1 Direct MCRT Simulation Results

The results obtained align well with those from Ciarniello et al. (2014) [17], showing the validity of the approach. A small discrepancy exists but can be attributed to random noise inherent to direct MCRT simulations and potential differences in phase function implementations. The Direct MCRT model was tested for specific geometries:

- $i = 30^\circ, b = 0, \phi = 0.2$
- $i = 60^\circ, b = -0.2, \phi = 0.05$

Figure 4.5: Direct MCRT simulation with literature results for $i=30^\circ, b=0, \phi=0.2$

Figure 4.6: Direct MCRT simulation with literature results for $i=60^\circ, b = -0.2, \phi = 0.05$

4.2.2 Indirect MCRT Simulation Results

Figure 4.7: Indirect isotropic MCRT method simulation with literature results.

The Indirect MCRT model was tested for several configurations:

Figure 4.8: Indirect MCRT method simulation with literature results.

All five plots matched the literature results by Ciarniello et al. 2014 [17] with good agreement. In case (d), a minor deviation is observed, likely due to stochastic variations or unaccounted shadowing effects at steep angles. This can be subject to further corrections.

4.2.3 Direct vs. Indirect MCRT Comparison

While both methods yield qualitatively similar curves, the Direct MCRT method exhibits significant noise and requires approximately 2.5 times more computational time. The Indirect method not only shows smoother results but is also more efficient and therefore

preferred for future applications. The results of the Direct and Indirect MCRT models were directly compared for:

- $i = 30^\circ, b = 0, \phi = 0.2$
- $i = 60^\circ, b = -0.2, \phi = 0.05$

(a) $i=30^\circ, b=0, \phi=0.2$

(b) $i=60^\circ, b=-0.2, \phi=0.1$

Figure 4.9: Direct MCRT against Indirect MCRT simulation

4.2.4 Validation Against HAPKE Isotropic Models

To validate the model further, the Indirect MCRT results were compared with:

- Ciarniello et al. 2014 MC simulations
- Hapke's IMSA model (with SHOE)
- Hapke's H2008 model

Figure 4.10: MCRT simulation against the literature results and Hapke models - IMSA (with SHOE) and H2008

The MCRT curves align closely with both the literature and IMSA models. While H2008 underestimates the brightness due to a lack of SHOE, the MCRT simulation accurately captures the backscattering peak, offering a better physical representation. This reinforces the credibility of the implemented opposition effect in the MCRT model.

4.2.5 Comparison with AMSA

Lastly, a comparison between the Indirect MCRT results and Hapke's AMSA model from Ciarniello et al. 2014 [17] reveals strong agreement. The AMSA model accounts for anisotropic multiple scattering, and the MCRT model effectively reproduces these

features. Despite the computational demand, MCRT remains advantageous due to its flexibility and physical accuracy.

Figure 4.11: MCRT simulation against the literature results and Hapke model - AMSA

The refined Indirect MCRT model shows substantial improvement over the earlier implementation and performs robustly when compared to both the Direct MCRT model and analytic models such as Hapke's. It is well-suited for simulating reflectance from particulate surfaces and can be used for further validation with lunar and Ceres data after a few more slight adjustments.

4.3 Discussions

This semester's work presents the development and refinement of a Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) model revised for simulating light interaction with airless planetary surfaces. The model was designed to provide a physically realistic approach to characterising the bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) in particulate media, where deterministic methods often fall short due to the complexity of multiple scattering, anisotropy, and irregular geometry.

A detailed implementation of both direct and indirect MCRT methods was carried out, and significant improvements in simulation accuracy were achieved during this

project. The refined Indirect MCRT model demonstrated excellent agreement with results from both analytical models (such as IMSA, AMSA, and H2008) and literature-based Monte Carlo results (notably Ciarniello et al. 2014). It successfully incorporated realistic optical properties such as single scattering albedo, filling factor, and anisotropic phase functions using the Henyey-Greenstein formulation. This version modelled the shadow-hiding opposition effect (SHOE) more accurately by simulating photon interactions based on intersection points rather than scattering at particle centres.

One of the significant distinctions observed between the direct and indirect approaches was the difference in noise levels and computational efficiency. The direct MCRT, while physically intuitive, was found to be significantly noisier and computationally more expensive. In contrast, the Indirect MCRT provided smoother and more reliable reflectance curves with relatively faster runtimes, making it a more feasible approach for future applications in planetary remote sensing.

Model validation with Hapke models showed that while the analytical models offer simplified theoretical understanding, the MCRT method, particularly in its indirect path, offers a more nuanced and flexible representation of the reflectance behaviour, especially near opposition, where SHOE dominates.

To evaluate the performance of the developed Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) models, we compared the simulated reflectance outputs with the semi-empirical model by Ciarniello et al. (2014) across three single scattering albedo values: 0.2, 0.5, and 0.7. The comparison was quantified using the coefficient of determination (R^2) to assess the goodness of fit.

Figure 4.12: MCRT simulation against Ciarniello et al 2014 for $i=30^\circ$, $b=0$, $\phi=0.2$

For the case of isotropic scattering, i.e $b=0$, $i=30^\circ$, and $\phi=0.2$, the model showed good agreement across all albedo values. For $\omega=0.7$, the Indirect MCRT reproduced the shape and magnitude of the reflectance with high fidelity, yielding $R^2=0.9406$ and for $\omega=0.5$ yielding $R^2=0.9231$. Even at low albedo ($\omega=0.2$), where photon statistics and angular scattering noise are more prominent, the model achieved a respectable agreement with $R^2=0.8325$. The indirect MCRT model performed well for anisotropic scattering as well, with R^2 values of 0.9556 and 0.9179 for $\omega=0.5$ and $\omega=0.7$, respectively. It captured the overall BRDF shape effectively in these regimes due to its efficient handling of multiple scattering. However, for the low albedo case ($\omega=0.2$), performance dropped to $R^2=0.8676$, likely due to reduced photon statistics and the dominance of single scattering, which increased angular noise.

The **Direct MCRT** model showed a good performance at high albedo ($\omega=0.7$), achieving $R^2=0.97$, reflecting its strength in accurately tracing multiple scattering paths and sharp angular features. However, its accuracy decreased slightly for lower albedo values, with $R^2=0.8669$ and $R^2=0.7452$, respectively. This reduction can be attributed to poor photon contribution in darker surfaces and the sensitivity of the model to photon depletion effects.

(a) Direct MCRT against Ciarniello et al. (2014)

(b) Indirect MCRT against Ciarniello et al. (2014)

Figure 4.13: Anisotropic: $i=60^\circ, b = -0.2, \phi = 0.05$

Despite these modifications, there are still areas where further enhancements can be made. These include reducing Monte Carlo noise without compromising accuracy, extending the model to wavelength-dependent scattering, and incorporating additional opposition effects such as the CBOE where relevant.

Conclusion

“Give up on your dreams and die”

— *Levi Ackerman: Attack on Titan*

Concluding this project, we present the formulation, development, and validation of a Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) model aimed at simulating the bidirectional reflectance of airless planetary surfaces with enhanced physical accuracy. Both Direct and Indirect MCRT approaches were implemented, allowing for a comparative evaluation of their performance in handling complex scattering phenomena. The Indirect MCRT method, in particular, showed notable advantages in terms of computational efficiency and noise reduction while successfully capturing key optical behaviors such as anisotropic scattering and the shadow-hiding opposition effect (SHOE). By incorporating physically realistic parameters - including single scattering albedo, filling factor, and anisotropic phase functions - the model offers a more representative description of light interaction in particulate media compared to conventional deterministic approaches.

The simulation outcomes were rigorously validated against several analytical Hapke-based models (IMSA, AMSA, and H2008) as well as literature-based Monte Carlo results, demonstrating strong consistency and reliability. These findings reinforce the MCRT framework’s capability to model subtle reflectance features, particularly near opposition, where analytical models often struggle. The work highlights the potential of the Indirect MCRT method as a robust tool for interpreting remote sensing observations and for retrieving surface properties of planetary bodies.

5.1 Future directions

Following validation along with improved implementation, this model can accurately simulate Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Functions (BRDF) which can be applied to observational data of nearly airless bodies, including laboratory-based lunar analogue to investigate its surface characteristics that could enable more precise interpretation of

observational data, aiding in the characterization of surface properties such as albedo, roughness, and particle size distribution.

One key direction is expanding the model to incorporate wavelength-dependent scattering, enabling more accurate simulations of spectral reflectance and allowing for detailed surface composition analysis. This would be particularly valuable for interpreting data from space missions and ground-based telescopes. Then the model can be applied to other planetary bodies that may have unique surface properties, providing an opportunity to further test and refine the model in varied environments. The model could also be expanded to include space weathering effects, such as micrometeorite impacts and solar wind, which alter surface properties over time. Alternative computational methods or optimisation techniques can be explored to reduce simulation runtime without compromising accuracy.

In conclusion, this work establishes a solid foundation for using Monte Carlo methods in planetary surface reflectance modelling. The results indicate that with further optimisations and extensions, the MCRT approach holds strong potential for interpreting and analysing remote sensing data from a range of airless planetary bodies, thereby contributing significantly to the field of planetary science.

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Appendices

Digging Deeper into MCRT Simulation

A.1 Direct MCRT Method

The Direct MCRT method involves simulating the paths of photon packets as they travel from the light source, through the medium, and towards the detector in the following process:

- **Initialisation:** Define the optical properties of the medium, including particle characteristics such as radius, single scattering albedo (SSA), and the single scattering phase function.
- Set up the original positions of the light source.
- **Interaction Probability:** Determine whether the photon is absorbed or scattered based on the SSA. If absorbed, the photon packet is removed from the simulation count. If scattered, the photon's direction is updated using the single scattering phase function $p(g)$.
- Determine the probability of absorption during each interaction. The probability of absorption is $1 - w$, where w is the SSA.
- Compare w to a random variable $v1$ uniformly distributed in the range $[0, 1]$. If $v1 > w$, then absorption occurs, and the photon's journey ends. Otherwise, the photon is scattered.
- If the photon is not absorbed, it is scattered to a new direction determined by a phase angle g . Calculate the probability as $dP(g) = p(g)dX = p(g)2\pi \sin(g)dg$, where $p(g)$ is the single scattering phase function.
- Generate a guess for g and compute $dP(g)/dg = p(g)2\pi \sin(g)$. Compare this value to a random variable $v2$ uniformly distributed in the range $[0, \text{MAX}(dP(g)/dg)]$. If $dP(g)/dg > v2$, then the guessed g is accepted; otherwise, generate a new guess until the condition is satisfied.

- The direction of the scattered photon is fully determined by both the phase angle g and the azimuthal angle ϕ . For spherical particles, scattering does not depend on the azimuth, so $\phi = 2\pi v_3$, where v_3 is a random variable uniformly distributed in the range $[0, 1]$.
- If the photon ‘z’ position exceeds the slab depth, it is considered to have escaped.
- **Photon Tracking:** Track the photons that escape from the medium and register their directions. Store the properties of the escaped photons.
- Repeat the process for a large number of photon packets (10^7 photons) to ensure statistical accuracy.
- Compute the reflectance scattered in each direction. This is proportional to the ratio between the number of stored scattered photons in that direction and the total number of photons propagated.

A.2 Indirect MCRT Method

The Indirect MCRT method, also known as backwards ray-tracing, focuses on tracing photon paths from the observer or detector backwards through the medium towards the light source. This method is efficient for capturing multiple scattering events and diffuse lighting conditions.

- **Initialisation:** Define the optical properties of the medium and the characteristics of the particles.
- **Photon Packet Generation:** Generate photon packets from the observer’s direction toward the medium. These packets have initial properties such as energy, direction, and position based on the observer’s viewpoint.
- **Photon Propagation:** Propagate the photon packet through the medium, reducing its energy by a factor w (SSA) after each scattering event.
- **Visibility Check:** Check if the photon packet can be traced back to the light source without obstruction. If visible, the photon packet contributes to the total energy reaching the observer.

- **Energy Accounting:** Use the phase angle g_i to compute the energy weight of the photon packet after each scattering event. Accumulate the energy contributions based on the single scattering phase function $p(g_i)$.
- **Multiple Scattering Handling:** Continue propagating the photon packet through multiple scattering events according to the interaction probability similar to the Direct MCRT method until it is either absorbed or leaves the medium. This process ensures that all significant scattering paths are considered.
- Repeat the process for a large number of photon packets (2×10^4 photons) to achieve statistical accuracy.
- Compute the reflectance by averaging the energy of the photon packets reaching the observer. This involves analysing the cumulative energy and angular distribution of the detected photons.

SIGNIFICANT FACTORS:

- Henyey-Greenstein Phase Function is used to determine the scattering angles of photons interacting with particles. This helps simulate realistic photon paths and energy distributions, which is essential for studying optical phenomena such as the Shadow Hiding Opposition Effect (SHOE) in a particulate medium. The phase function $p(g)$ describes light scattering by individual particles and is also given by the extended double-lobed HG function:

$$p(g) = \frac{1+c}{2} \left(\frac{1-b^2}{(1-2b\cos g+b^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) + \frac{1-c}{2} \left(\frac{1-b^2}{(1+2b\cos g+b^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

- Reflectance $r(i, e, g)$: The ratio of the reflected light to the incident light for given incidence, emission, and phase angles.

Model Initialization

The initial assumptions and photon conditions for the simulation are:

- Particle Radius (r_0): We assume a typical particle radius $r_0 = 1 \mu m$ based on common regolith grain sizes observed on airless planetary surfaces, such as the Moon. So the scattering is taken to be in the Geometric Optics Limits ($r_0 \gg \lambda$) [18].
- Filling Factor (ϕ): The filling factor represents the fraction of the slab's volume occupied by particles. For this case, a typical value of $\phi = 0.2$ (i.e., 20% of the volume is filled with particles) is assumed.
- Transmission Requirement: The transmission of light through the slab is required to be less than 1%, i.e., $P_{\text{trans}} < 0.01$, to ensure sufficient interaction of photons within the slab.
- Photon packets start from the origin '(0, 0, 0)'.
- Initial direction of photons is determined by the incidence angle.
- Initial energy ' E_0 ' of photon packets is set to 1.0.
- Initial visibility ' h_i ' of the photon is set to 1.

B.1 Photon Trajectory

To support debugging, photon paths were spatially simulated for 1000 packets at varying incidence angles and albedos, allowing visualisation of propagation in 2D without excessive runtimes.

APPENDIX B. MODEL INITIALIZATION

(a) $i = 0^\circ$, $b=0$

(b) $i = 30^\circ$, $b = 0.5$

(c) $i = 30^\circ$, $b = -0.5$

Figure B.1: Trials for photon propagation with $N = 1000$ (all), $SSA=0.2$ (top row) and $SSA=0.7$ (bottom row).

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Abstract

MONTE CARLO RADIATIVE TRANSFER MODEL FOR AIRLESS PLANETARY SURFACES

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Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) is a method that simulates light interaction by ray tracing in particulate media and analyses the BRDF of such surfaces through random sampling. The key objective is to create a robust MCRT algorithm that incorporates surface characteristics to simulate the interaction of light without clouds, which in turn characterizes the surface properties. To validate the model's accuracy, outputs will be compared with the widely used Hapke model. Following validation, the MCRT model will be applied to observational data of nearly airless bodies, including laboratory-based lunar data and space-based observations of Ceres to investigate its surface characteristics and provide insights into its formation and evolution in the solar system.

Using Monte Carlo ray-tracing, we will simulate the photon propagation to obtain the photometric output of media with different porosities and scattering behaviours (isotropic, back-scattering and forward-scattering). The progress of this work has resulted in a comprehensive understanding of the reflectance behaviour and surface dynamics of these bodies. By comparing model predictions with analytical solutions, the project enhances the accuracy of interpreting planetary surface properties from remote sensing observations. Challenges remain in fine-tuning the path tracing to account for opposition effects and refining the spatial resolution of the single scattering events. Future plans include the incorporation of these modifications appropriately and conducting a detailed analysis of spectral data from space missions. This will help refine parameters like emissivity and albedo maps at a lower computational expense.

“Mischief Managed”

— Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban —